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Original Research

In Vitro Evaluation of physical and mechanical properties of different Interocclusal Record Materials at Room Temperature and Simulated Intraoral Condition

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Interocclusal records that are made with the use of the right material - technique would require minimal occlusal adjustments in the patient's mouth and would significantly contribute to the success of rehabilitation procedures in terms of function and aesthetics. **Methods:** A total of 80 samples of four interocclusal recording materials were prepared, with 20 samples per group, each divided into two subgroups: room temperature and simulated intraoral conditions and manipulated according to manufacturer instructions and subjected to a load of 5.59 N using a glass plate and weights, then allowed to set. Testing was conducted at room temperature and under simulated intraoral conditions (37 °C, 100% humidity, artificial saliva). Flow was assessed by measuring surface area using a scanner and AR Ruler digital software, while hardness was evaluated using a Shore A test. **Results:** Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, Tukey's post-hoc test, and unpaired t-test with significance at $p < 0.05$. At room temperature and simulated intraoral conditions, the highest flow was recorded in the ZOE group ($10.60 \pm 1.26 \text{ cm}^2$), followed by polyether ($8.65 \pm 0.54 \text{ cm}^2$), polyvinyl siloxane ($3.84 \pm 0.46 \text{ cm}^2$), and bite registration wax ($3.05 \pm 0.41 \text{ cm}^2$). While for Hardness, a statistically significant difference was observed among all groups, At both room temperature and simulated intraoral conditions, Polyvinyl siloxane showed the highest hardness, followed by ZOE, while polyether and bite registration wax exhibited lower values. **Conclusion:** Statistically significant differences were observed in the flow of ZOE and polyvinyl siloxane and in the hardness of ZOE between room temperature and simulated intraoral conditions.

Keywords: Interocclusal recording materials, Polyvinylsiloxane, zinc oxide eugenol paste, Polyether, Aluwax.

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INTRODUCTION

The specialty of prosthodontics deals with the rehabilitation of structure, function and aesthetics with the help of an appropriate prosthesis. One of the key requirements in any prosthesis fabrication is recording maximum intercuspation.¹ Hence, Interocclusal recording materials should have desirable physical and mechanical properties like flow and hardness to record proper intercuspation relationship. Materials used to

record interocclusal relation are known as interocclusal record materials or bite registration materials. Primary purpose of an interocclusal record is to provide horizontal stability and transfer the maximum intercuspation on the articulator. Interocclusal bite registration materials help in delivering the precise and high quality of final prosthetic restoration. So minimal adjustment requires.^{2,3}

The first interocclusal registration was introduced in 1756 as natural waxes. Other materials include impression plaster, waxes, zinc oxide eugenol, acrylic resin, hydrocolloids. Recently elastomeric materials like polyether and polyvinyl siloxane have been widely used.^{4,5}

Flow is the property of a material to change its shape under the influence of external load or under its weight. Good flow characteristics and limited initial resistance to closure are desirable properties for bite registration materials prior to set.⁶ The recording material, which is initially soft and harden after setting is used to record interocclusal relation. The hardened material is then transferred onto the casts to be mounted on an articulator.

METHODS

Study Design:

In vitro experimental study

Four different interocclusal record materials were used as zinc oxide eugenol paste (DPI), bite registration wax (MAARC), polyvinyl siloxane (Orangebite, Medicept), and polyether (Impregum Soft, 3M). To evaluate a flow and hardness of interocclusal materials at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition grouping of test samples were made as follows; total of 80 samples were used, 40 samples were tested at room temperature and 40 under simulated intraoral conditions. Each group included 10 samples, each of zinc oxide eugenol, bite registration wax, polyvinyl siloxane, and polyether. (Figure-1)

Figure-1: Grouping of interocclusal record materials test samples

• **Manipulation of Materials-**

- Zinc oxide eugenol was prepared by mixing equal portions of base and accelerator until uniform, loaded into a syringe, and 0.5 ml was dispensed onto a cellophane-covered glass slab without air entrapment.
- Bite registration wax was softened in a 45 °C water bath for 5 minutes inside a syringe and then dispensed onto a glass slab.
- Polyvinyl siloxane was directly dispensed onto the glass slab using an auto-mixing cartridge system.
- Polyether was mixed in equal proportions of base and catalyst to make homogeneous mix, loaded

into a syringe, and 0.5 ml was dispensed onto a cellophane-covered glass slab and avoided air bubbles.

• **Fabrication of Samples-**

- After manipulation, glass plate of approximately 70 gm was placed over materials followed by 500 gm weight. A total 5.59 N weight was applied. This pressure was required to compensate initial resistance to closure of interocclusal record material which may vary between 0.5 N to 13.8 N. Each material is allowed to set for recommended setting time plus additional 6 minutes.⁷

- This procedure was carried out under two conditions.⁶
 - a) at room temperature (Figure 2)
 - b) Simulated intraoral condition (at 37° C in 100% humidity and specimen immersed in artificial saliva in incubator) (Figure 3)
- Artificial saliva was prepared in the laboratory using 0.4 gm sodium chloride, 0.4 gm potassium chloride, 0.69 gm sodium dihydrogen dehydrate, 0.005 gm hydrated sodium sulphide, 1 gm urea and 1000 ml of deionized water. 10 gm sodium hydroxide was added to adjust pH to 6.75.

Figure- 2 (Samples at room temperature)

Figure- 3 (Samples at simulated intraoral condition)

- **Evaluation of Flow and Hardness-**
 - Flow was determined by calculating the surface area covered by material and recorded with scanner with use of AR Ruler digital software.⁷
 - Hardness was tested with Shore A Hardness Tester and depth indicator was set to zero and light force was applied with the index finger to the indenter until the presser foot is in full contact with sample and values were recorded.⁸

RESULTS

Data were collected from 80 samples and tabulated and statistical analysis was done using SPSS software (IBM SPSS Statistical software version 20) ZOE ($10.60 \pm 1.26 \text{ cm}^2$) had highest mean value of flow and Bite registration wax ($2.85 \pm 0.40 \text{ cm}^2$) had least mean value of flow at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition among all tested material. (Table-1-shows the mean value of flow of different interocclusal record materials using ANOVA test.

TABLE 1: MEAN VALUE OF FLOW OF INTEROCCLUSAL RECORD MATERIALS					
Condition	Groups	Number	Flow(cm^2)		P Value
			Mean	SD	
Room temperature	ZOE	10	10.60	1.26	$\leq 0.001^*$
	Bite registration wax	10	3.05	0.41	
	Polyvinylsiloxane	10	3.84	0.46	
	Polyether	10	8.65	0.54	
Simulated intra oral condition	ZOE	10	9.15	1.08	$\leq 0.001^*$
	Bite registration wax	10	2.85	0.40	
	Polyvinylsiloxane	10	3.33	0.31	
	Polyether	10	8.24	0.67	

P Value (All groups and conditions) = 0.039*

Level of Significance $P \leq 0.05$, * Significant, ** Non-Significant

TABLE 2 COMPARISON OF FLOW OF INTEROCCLUSAL RECORD MATERIALS			
Conditions	Groups		P Value
Room temperature	ZOE	Bite registration wax	≤ 0.001*
		Polyvinylsiloxane	≤ 0.001*
		Polyether	≤ 0.001*
	Bite registration wax	Polyvinylsiloxane	0.111**
		Polyether	≤ 0.001*
		Polyvinylsiloxane	≤ 0.001*
Simulated intra oral condition	ZOE	Bite registration wax	≤ 0.001*
		Polyvinylsiloxane	≤ 0.001*
		Polyether	0.029*
	Bite registration wax	Polyvinylsiloxane	0.415**
		Polyether	≤ 0.001*
		Polyether	≤ 0.001*

Level of Significance P ≤ 0.05, * Significant, ** Non-Significant

An Intergroup comparison of flow of different interocclusal record materials using a Post Hoc Tukey HSD test showed at room temperature, ZOE exhibited significantly higher flow compared to bite registration wax, polyvinylsiloxane, and polyether. Significant differences were also found between bite registration wax and polyether, as well as between polyvinylsiloxane and polyether. However, no significant difference was observed between bite registration wax and polyvinylsiloxane. At simulated intraoral conditions, significant differences in flow were noted among all groups, except between bite registration wax and polyvinylsiloxane, where the difference was not significant. (Table 2-shows the

intergroup comparison of flow of different interocclusal record materials using a Post Hoc Tukey HSD test) Comparison of flow of different interocclusal record materials at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition using Unpaired t test showed statistically significant reduction in flow was observed at room temperature and at simulated intraoral conditions in both the ZOE and polyvinylsiloxane groups, with higher mean values recorded at room temperature ZOE: $10.60 \pm 1.26 \text{ cm}^2$ and polyvinylsiloxane $3.84 \pm 0.46 \text{ cm}^2$ In contrast, bite registration wax and polyether showed no statistically significant difference between the two conditions.(Graph-1)

(Graph-1 shows the comparison of flow of different interocclusal record materials at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition)

Polyvinylsiloxane group (77.20 ± 2.44) had highest mean value of hardness and Bite registration wax group (43.60 ± 1.35) had least mean value of hardness at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition among all tested material. (Table 3- shows the mean value of hardness of different interocclusal record materials using an ANOVA test.

TABLE 3 MEAN VALUE OF HARDNESS OF INTEROCCLUSAL RECORD MATERIALS					
Condition	Groups	Number	Hardness		P Value
			Mean	SD	
Room temperature	ZOE	10	65.90	1.85	$\leq 0.001^*$
	Bite registration wax	10	43.60	1.35	
	Polyvinylsiloxane	10	77.20	2.44	
	Polyether	10	46.00	1.33	
Simulated intra oral condition	ZOE	10	70.90	1.72	$\leq 0.001^*$
	Bite registration wax	10	44.70	2.86	
	Polyvinylsiloxane	10	77.20	2.34	
	Polyether	10	47.30	1.49	
P Value (All groups and conditions) = 0.001^*					

Level of Significance $P \leq 0.05$, * Significant, ** Non-Significant

The intergroup comparison of mean hardness of different interocclusal record materials using a Post Hoc Tukey HSD test showed that ZOE showed significantly higher hardness compared to bite registration wax, polyvinylsiloxane, and polyether. Significant differences were also observed between bite registration wax and polyvinylsiloxane, as well as between polyvinylsiloxane and polyether. However, no significant difference was found between bite registration wax and polyether in both the conditions.

TABLE 4 COMPARISON OF MEAN HARDNESS OF INTEROCCLUSAL RECORD MATERIALS			
Condition	Groups		P Value
Room temperature	ZOE	Bite registration wax	$\leq 0.001^*$
		Polyvinylsiloxane	$\leq 0.001^*$
		Polyether	$\leq 0.001^*$
	Bite registration wax	Polyvinylsiloxane	$\leq 0.001^*$
		Polyether	0.025^*
		Polyvinylsiloxane	$\leq 0.001^*$
Simulated intra oral condition	ZOE	Bite registration wax	$\leq 0.001^*$
		Polyvinylsiloxane	$\leq 0.001^*$
		Polyether	$\leq 0.001^*$
	Bite registration wax	Polyvinylsiloxane	$\leq 0.001^*$
		Polyether	0.053^{**}
		Polyvinylsiloxane	$\leq 0.001^*$

Level of Significance $P \leq 0.05$, * Significant, ** Non-Significant

Comparison of hardness of different interocclusal record materials at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition using Unpaired t test showed that statistically significant increase in hardness was observed in the ZOE group under simulated intraoral conditions compared to room temperature (70.90 ± 1.72 vs 65.90 ± 1.85). In contrast, bite registration wax, polyvinylsiloxane, and polyether showed no significant difference in hardness between the two conditions. (Graph-2)

Graph 4 shows the comparison of hardness of different interocclusal record materials at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition.

DISCUSSION

For successful rehabilitation, the fabrication of prosthesis should be harmonious with the stomatognathic system. This requires meticulous recording of existing intercuspation which can be achieved with the help of interocclusal records.

In present study, a statistically significant difference was present in mean values of flow and hardness among all groups in which higher mean value of flow was seen in ZOE group and higher mean value of hardness was seen in Polyvinylsiloxane group and least mean values of flow and hardness was seen in bite registration wax at both room temperature and at simulated intraoral condition.

These findings are consistent with the study done by Michalakakis KX et al, reported that polyvinyl siloxane exhibited the least flow, followed by polyether and zinc oxide–eugenol in increasing order. They attributed the low flow of polyvinyl siloxane to its high consistency, rapid polymer chain formation, and quick transition from the plastic to elastic phase.⁷

Study conducted by Chandak et al evaluated a flow of four different ZOE at room temperature and in simulated intraoral condition and found that flow of ZOE group was reduced in the presence of saliva and with the increase in the temperature.⁷ Lassila reported that the initial resistance to closure of various materials ranged from 0.5 N to 13.8 N. Based on this, a total load of 570 g (5.59 N) was applied during sample fabrication in the present in-vitro study.⁶

Chai et al. emphasized that an ideal registration material should offer minimal resistance during jaw closure to maintain the established vertical dimension, as

excessive viscosity may cause mandibular deviation from its normal intercuspal position. Additionally, the material should be sufficiently rigid to prevent deformation under the weight of the casts and articulator during mounting.⁹ Gurav SV et al, evaluated 40 samples and concluded that zinc oxide–eugenol exhibited the highest flow compared to polyether, polyvinyl siloxane, and bite registration wax. Its minimal resistance to mandibular closure allows a more accurate interocclusal relationship, supporting the findings of the present study.⁹

Arjun N. Mithra et al, did study in which they had evaluated the hardness of polyvinylsiloxane and polyether bite registration material using Shore A hardness tester, total 30 samples were fabricated and found that polyvinylsiloxane had greatest surface hardness than polyether.¹⁰ Srinivas et al. supported the present findings by evaluating the hardness of various polyvinyl siloxane and bite registration wax materials using a Shore A hardness tester. Total 360 samples were evaluated and found that higher hardness values for polyvinyl siloxane compared to bite registration wax.¹¹ The present findings are supported by Kumar et al., who reported that polyvinylsiloxane exhibited the highest surface hardness, followed by zinc oxide–eugenol paste and bite registration wax in descending order.¹² Yash Madaan et al tested the hardness of interocclusal record material like Polyvinylsiloxane, Aluwax, and Zinc oxide eugenol interocclusal record material after disinfection with iodophor and found that Polyvinylsiloxane had the highest surface hardness followed by ZOE and Aluwax and concluded that

hardness was not affected by disinfection which positively supports the results of present study.¹³

CONCLUSION

In this study, physical property like flow and mechanical property like hardness of the different interocclusal record materials were evaluated at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition and within the limitations of the study, following conclusions can be drawn.

1. ZOE had greatest flow amongst all tested materials followed by polyether, polyvinylsiloxane and bite registration wax respectively both at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition.
2. There was a statistically significant difference in flow at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition in ZOE and polyvinylsiloxane.
3. Polyvinylsiloxane had highest hardness amongst all tested materials followed by ZOE, polyether and bite registration wax respectively both at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition.
4. There was a statistically significant difference in hardness of ZOE at room temperature and simulated intraoral condition.

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